

Conductometric Study on the Quantitative Precipitation of Praseodymium(III) as Normal Tellurite

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Conductometric determination of Pr^{3+} has been carried out at $25^{\circ}\pm 0.5^{\circ}$ by titrating it against sodium tellurite solution in 10% ethanol. An overall effect of ethanol concentration on the results has also been studied. The sharp breaks obtained at the end point in direct as well as reverse titrations lend support to the formation of normal praseodymium tellurite (molar ratio of Pr: Te being 2:3). Being a simple and precise titrimetric procedure, the method is advantageous for the determination of Pr^{3+} in micro quantities.

Tellurite ion has been successfully used in the micro-determination of several cations¹⁻⁴. Recently it has been observed³⁻⁴ that a number of metals may be precipitated quantitatively by addition of sodium or potassium tellurite under appropriate conditions and the precipitation reactions may be utilised for the conductometric and/or amperometric estimation of the metals.

Various methods have been developed for the micro-determination of praseodymium, but the conductometric low-frequency titrations have seldom been used for its determination. The present communication records the results of a series of conductometric titrations of praseodymium nitrate with sodium tellurite under varied experimental conditions and develops a method for the determination of Pr^{3+} as normal tellurite on a micro-scale.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium tellurite (B.D.H.) and praseodymium nitrate (A.R., Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay) were dissolved separately in conductivity water. Tellurium was estimated as metallic tellurium⁵ and praseodymium as Pr_2O_3 ⁶. Solutions of lower concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilution.

A Mullard conductivity bridge, type E 7506, a.c. line-operated, direct reading electronic instrument, with an electron-beam indicator for the balance, was used for measurements of the conductance.

When the titrations were carried out in aqueous medium, low results were obtained which improved on addition of ethanol. Several titrations were therefore carried out at

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4. Prasad and Kumar, *Proc. Inst. Chem. India*, 1958, 25, 4.
5. Lenher and Homberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 387.
6. Spaen *et al.*, *Acad. R.P.R., Stud. Oerost Chim.*, 1963, II(2), 247.

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different ethanol concentrations ranging from 0-25%, of which 10 to 15% provided the best results.

In the final method adopted for titrations, different volumes of praseodymium nitrate solution containing 10% of ethanol were taken in the cell and placed on the magnetic stirrer. The electrodes were dipped into the test solution and the initial conductance was recorded. Sodium tellurite solution was added from a micro-burette in small amounts, the mixture stirred well, and the reading recorded after allowing the precipitate to settle. The end point was obtained graphically by plotting the conductance against the volume of the titrant. A similar procedure was adopted in the case of reverse titrations.

FIG. 1
Sodium tellurite added (ml).

Praseodymium nitrate solutions at concentrations between 0.9891×10^{-4} and $2.130 \times 10^{-4}M$ were successfully titrated with sodium tellurite ($2.527 \times 10^{-2}M$). In the reverse titrations, sodium tellurite solutions (1.894×10^{-4} to $2.315 \times 10^{-4}M$) were titrated with praseodymium nitrate solution of concentration $7.416 \times 10^{-3}M$. The method is reproducible and has an accuracy of 0.5—1%. Fig. 1 represents one typical curve each from direct and reverse titrations. Curve A represents direct titration and curve B, reverse titration.

DISCUSSION

The reaction involved in the present titration may be represented as

The reaction is quantitative and stoichiometric and lends support to the formation of $\text{Pr}_2(\text{TeO}_3)_3$. In direct titration (Fig. 1) in pre-equivalence region, when sodium tellurite solution is added, a decrease in conductance is observed, which may be attributed to the removal of Pr^{3+} ions from the solution, but after equivalent point there is a steep increase in conductance, due to the dissociation of Na_2TeO_3 added in excess to the solution.

In reverse titration, the nature of the curve shows a steady increase in conductance up to the equivalence point because of the substitution of TeO_3^{2-} ions by more mobile NO_3^- ions. In post-equivalence region, there is a sharp increase in conductance of the solution due to the contribution of Pr^{3+} and NO_3^- ions to the solution as $\text{Pr}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ is being added gradually.

The necessity of using ethanol during these sets of titrations arose because of the dissolution, dissociation, and hydrolysis of the precipitate in aqueous medium, which were prevented by addition of ethanol, the optimum ethanolic concentration being 10%. Thus the present method is a simple titrimetric procedure for micro-determination of Pr^{3+} .

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